

THE IMPACT OF BAD HABITS ON A PERSON'S OVERALL PHYSICAL FITNESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15344618>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the impact of various bad habits on physical fitness and the level of human activity, identifying the most pressing and problematic issues of this topic, describing the negative effects of addictions on humans and finding solutions to eliminate them.*

Keywords: *physical fitness, bad habits, addiction, withdrawal, consequences.*

Introduction. Physical activity is an essential factor in the life of every person. It promotes the development of muscle and motor apparatus, improves coordination of movements, strengthens bones and reduces the risk of diseases such as diabetes, obesity and cardiovascular diseases. In this article, we will consider the impact of bad habits on a person's overall physical fitness and propose strategies to eliminate negative effects and improve the condition of the human body as a whole.

Methodology. Currently, we can identify an extensive list of so-called human addictions from harmless at first glance to extremely dangerous: unhealthy diet, insufficient hygiene, excessive spending time on various gadgets and computer games, alcohol abuse, smoking, the use of narcotic and psychotropic substances, incorrectly adjusted daily and sleep patterns, and many others. We will describe in more detail some of them.

1. Alcohol consumption. This problem is one of the most common and raises many questions and debates about the harm of alcohol, as some people mistakenly believe that alcohol-containing products can help eliminate not only ailments, but also improve the effectiveness of training. However, studying this problem can completely refute this theory, let's give an example of some variants of the negative effects of the substances under discussion. Any drink contains ethanol in its composition, which in turn provokes the formation of blood clots, and oxygen levels decrease. Also:

1) alcohol and alcohol-containing products can reduce endurance and impair athletic performance (these substances cause dilation of blood vessels, which can lead to a decrease in blood flow to muscles and organs, which, in turn, can worsen athletic performance);

2) the effect on movement coordination and reaction (this can lead to incorrect and inaccurate movements in terms of technique and tactics, which can subsequently increase the risk of injury and significantly reduce athletic performance);

3) the effect on recovery after exercise (alcohol causes disorders in the immune system and can reduce blood flow to the muscles, as mentioned earlier, therefore, a person will slow down not only the recovery process after physical exertion, but also gradually decrease the level of fitness and endurance);

4) deterioration of the vital organ — the liver and poor glucose metabolism, this substance is a source of energy for muscle growth, processed by the liver;

5) the hormonal background is disrupted (most alcoholic beverages contain estrogen-like components that increase the level of estrogen, and, unfortunately, lower the level of testosterone,

this problem can be especially significant for those who care about the appearance of the body, since in such cases men have rounded hips, arms and abdomen).

In addition to the above negative consequences, alcohol abuse can lead to rapid weight gain, overweight, sleep disorders and insomnia, dehydration and intoxication of the body, a decrease in brain volume, and an increased risk of developing cancer.

2. Smoking. In this case, the situation is similar to the description of the harm of alcoholic beverages, there is an opinion that the use of tobacco and nicotine helps to control weight and eliminate the regularly occurring feeling of hunger, however, the issue of weight loss in such cases is still poorly understood. Most scientists and doctors hold the position that smoking negatively affects a person's physical fitness and can lead to various diseases.

First, smoking reduces physical endurance, as it restricts blood flow to muscles and organs, reduces the number of blood vessels, and, like alcohol, causes a lack of oxygen and various nutrients, which can lead not only to a deterioration in metabolism, but also to athletic performance in general, complicating the recovery process after exercise.

Secondly, smoking increases the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases such as atherosclerosis, myocardial infarction and stroke. These problems are almost the first on the list of contraindications to sports, especially such as athletics, running.

Thirdly, the bones of a smoker become less strong and strong, the risk of injury and its complications increases, and recovery from them takes many times longer, bones heal more slowly, tendon degeneration or inflammation of the joint bags is likely to develop. Smoking can lead to many terrible diseases, such as chronic bronchitis and emphysema of the lungs, cause the risk of developing lung cancer and other types of malignant tumors, which can also lead to a decrease in athletic endurance, not to mention a deterioration in overall health and quality of life.

3. The use of narcotic and psychotropic substances. These substances can be classified as the most dangerous bad habits, and their harm cannot be fully described, since they are the ones that in most cases lower a person to the bottom of the social system. They affect the hormonal system of a person, changing his mental and physical condition. Drugs can have a negative effect on a person's physical fitness through various mechanisms:

1) hormonal system (decrease in the level of components responsible for physical fitness, such as testosterone and ghrelin);

2) the cardiovascular system (impaired blood flow to muscles and organs, as well as a decrease in the overall performance of the heart);

3) nervous system (such substances cause depression of the central nervous system, possibly deterioration of coordination of movements, decreased reaction speed, concentration of attention and decrease in tactical skills, despite the fact that drugs can reduce painful experience and reduce the feeling of pain, they can also cause weakness, fatigue);

4) respiratory system (during the direct action of the substance, the respiratory rate decreases and, eventually, this can lead to insufficient oxygen supply to organs and tissues);

5) the immune system (according to medical research, drug-addicted people significantly deviate from the norm in a smaller number of immune cells, such as lymphocytes; accordingly, their body produces too few antibodies, which are responsible for fighting viruses and infectious diseases).

Results and discussion. Prolonged use of psychotropic and narcotic drugs can lead to the development of physical dependence, as the body adapts to the presence of the substance and

requires more to achieve the same effect. In addition, they have a negative impact on the human psyche and personality, leading to an immoral lifestyle. Addiction can often provoke a destructive effect, the occurrence of mental disorders, changes in personal qualities, character traits, changes in priorities and moral values, deterioration of mental abilities and memory, and in some cases its complete loss.

In general, drugs can significantly affect athletic training and performance, and their use can lead to serious health and sports career problems. It is better to choose a healthy lifestyle and athletic methods to achieve success in sports. Getting rid of bad habits depends on many factors, including motivation, the desire for change, and the support of the environment.

If we talk about alcohol, drug use or smoking, modern medicine has developed universal and effective methods, from sprays to eliminate nicotine addiction to long-term rehabilitation centers for people suffering from drug addiction. And we, in turn, have identified the most appropriate overall strategy to combat bad habits.:

1. Identify the habits that you need to change.
2. Develop a strategy to change these habits. This may include setting goals, planning actions, and using motivation techniques.
3. Create a positive environment for change. This means that you need to surround yourself with people who support you in your attempt to change habits, and create conditions that contribute to your success.
4. Use self-control techniques to stop yourself when you notice that you are about to break down.
5. Don't be afraid to make mistakes. Changing habits can be a difficult process, and you may encounter setbacks. Keep trying, considering your mistakes and improving your methods.
6. Reward yourself for progress. When you succeed in changing your habits, allow yourself to feel proud and celebrate your achievements.
7. Don't be afraid to ask for help. If you need additional support, do not hesitate to contact friends, family, or professionals such as psychologists or coaches.
8. Remember that changing habits can be a long and difficult process, but with perseverance, patience, and support, you can overcome bad habits and become a better person.

After getting rid of a particular bad habit, it is necessary to achieve the highest or previous level of physical fitness, for this you can use the following methods:

1. Setting goals and planning (it is necessary to set specific goals for the level of physical activity and develop an action plan to achieve these goals).
2. Regular physical activity (engaging in regular physical activity activities such as walking, running, cycling, or gym workouts).
3. Integration of physical activity into daily life (search for alternatives, for example, prioritizing cycling or walking, using stairs instead of elevators, etc.).
4. A variety of types of physical activity (swimming, light or heavy athletics, dancing, gymnastics).
5. Consideration of individual characteristics (when planning physical activity, it is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics and capabilities of a person in order to avoid injury and accelerate the achievement of goals).

6. Compliance with the sleep regime (sleep is an indispensable component of a healthy lifestyle and physical fitness, since at this time the human body secretes growth hormone, which is responsible for the repair of tissues and the bone system).

7. Healthy and nutritious nutrition (this factor can help not only in regulating body weight and losing weight, since proper food, once in the body, triggers the activation of all metabolic processes that are extremely important for both weight gain and body recovery).

Conclusion. In conclusion, we can conclude that for a full-fledged healthy life, a person needs to eliminate bad habits from their lifestyle using a certain technique, as well as regularly engage in various sports disciplines to maintain physical fitness and general fitness levels.

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